

A Nonparametric Ordering-Based Probabilistic Regression with Rank-Adaptive Coefficient Functions

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Appendix 1: Estimating the empirical distributions of the Base coefficients

This appendix explains the procedure and formulas for estimating the empirical distribution of the base coefficients of the probabilistic model. The estimation of base coefficients is illustrated in Error! Reference source not found. The process consists, in general, of finding the linear combinations of the independent variables $X_1 \dots X_k \dots X_K$ that maximizes Y_0 (or number of zeros) in a window C_{r_0} and Y_1 (or number of ones) in a window C_{r_1} .

C_{r_0} is the window that moves from left to right during the maximization of Y_0 , as the upper part of Figure 1 shows, and C_{r_1} moves from right to left to maximize Y_1 , as the middle part presents. r_0 and r_1 are the subindices that number the linear combinations that maximize Y_0 and Y_1 in the window C_{r_0} and C_{r_1} , respectively. The sizes of C_{r_0} and C_{r_1} are m observations each and comprise three parts of size p . In Figure 1, we observe that C_2 ($r_0=2$) overlaps with the last two parts of C_1 and with the first two of C_3 . In general, C_{r_0} overlaps with the last two parts of C_{r_0-1} and the first two of C_{r_0+1} , and the same occurs for C_{r_1} . The objective of the overlapping is to smooth the changes in the coefficients. Only C_1 ($r_0=1$ or $r_1=1$) does not overlap with the preceding window since it is the first window.

$P_{r_0}(X)$ and $L_{r_1}(X)$ are the linear combinations of the independent variables $X_1 \dots X_k \dots X_K$ that maximize Y_0 and Y_1 in C_{r_0} and C_{r_1} , respectively. $P_{r_0}(X)$ and $L_{r_1}(X)$ are estimated using an

iterative process that will be explained later. $R-1$ is the total number of linear combinations we estimate when Y_0 or Y_1 are maximized separately. Using the results of maximizing Y_0 and Y_1 together, we obtain R linear equations, whose coefficients are the base coefficients for obtaining the *Rank-Adaptive Coefficient Functions* of the dependent variables.

S_{r_0} and T_{r_1} are integer-valued rank indices. The quantity S_{r_0} denotes the rank position of the observation at which the linear combination, $P_{r_0}(X)$ is estimated. Similarly, T_{r_1} represents the rank position associated with the linear combination, $L_{r_1}(X)$. From Figure 1, it follows that the indices satisfy the mirror relationship $r_1=R+1-r_0$, implying that the corresponding rank locations coincide, i.e., $S_{r_0}=T_{r_1}=R+1-r_0$. For example, when $R=10$ and $r_0=6$, we obtain $r_1=5$, so S_6 and T_5 correspond to the same rank location. The point S_1 denotes the rank associated with the linear combination $P_1(X)$, and it equals $m/2$, which corresponds to the midpoint of window C_1 . The midpoint of window C_2 is located at $m/2+p$, so that $S_2= m/2+p$, with associated linear combinations $P_2(X)$ and $L_9(X)$. Likewise, the midpoint of window C_3 is $m/2+2p$, implying $S_3= m/2+2p$, with corresponding linear combinations $P_3(X)$ and $L_8(X)$.

More generally, for $r_0= 2, \dots, R-1$, the rank location at which the paired linear combinations $P_{r_0}(X)$ and $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$ are estimated is given by

$$S_{r_0} = \frac{m}{2} + (r_0 - 1)p$$

At the upper boundary, corresponding to S_R , only the linear combination $L_1(X)$ is the estimated linear combination. Similarly, at the lower boundary S_1 , only $P_1(X)$.

To estimate $P_1(X)$ at the rank location S_1 , we evaluate multiple candidate linear combinations and select the one that maximizes the concentration of $Y=0$, Y_0 , within window C_1 . Once

$P_1(X)$ is obtained, its value is computed for all observations, which are subsequently ranked according to this score. After sorting the observations by $P_1(X)$, the window C_{r0} shifts forward by p observations — from C_1 to C_2 — discarding the first p observations, as illustrated in Figure 1. At the next midpoint S_2 , the linear combination $P_2(X)$ that maximizes Y_0 within window C_2 is estimated. The observations are then re-ranked according to $P_2(X)$, and the window advances again by p observations, moving from C_2 to C_3 . This iterative procedure continues sequentially until $r_0=R-1$, corresponding to window C_{R-1} , as depicted in Figure 1. The process generates a sequence of paired linear combinations, $P_{r_0}(X)$ and $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$, each associated with a specific rank location S_{r_0} . The outcomes are highlighted in grey in Figure 1, while the correspondence between $P_{r_0}(X)$, $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$ and S_{r_0} is indicated by the arrows.

Since $P_{r_0}(X)$ is obtained by maximizing Y_0 and $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$ is obtained by maximizing Y_1 , the associated coefficient vectors are oriented in opposite directions. Consequently, a predictor X_k with a positive coefficient in $P_{r_0}(X)$ has a negative coefficient in $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$ and vice versa. Moreover, the intercept of $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$ follows a complementary normalization rule, such that it equals one minus the intercept of $P_{r_0}(X)$. Therefore, before pooling the results, the coefficients from $L_{R+1-r_0}(X)$ are transformed to align their sign and intercept orientation with those of $P_{r_0}(X)$, yielding a consistent set of base coefficients.

Algorithm to find the Base Coefficients

The full algorithm is illustrated in Figure 5 using the maximization of Y_0 as an example. The procedure begins by selecting the total number of linear equations, R , the size of the window m or the overlapping size p . If R is chosen, given a population of size Pop , the other two key

structural parameters are then defined. Specifically, the window size is computed as $m=3\text{Pop}/(R+2)$, and the overlap size is set to $p=m/3$. Each window C_{r0} contains $m=3p$ observations, ensuring that consecutive windows partially overlap and allowing the algorithm to capture smooth changes in the coefficient structure across the ranking.

The second step consists of evaluating B alternative linear combinations of the independent variables within the first window C_1 . This evaluation is an iterative process.¹ Like other population-based search strategies, the iterative process is based on nature, specifically natural selection.

These B candidate combinations are generated and assessed in g groups of size n , so that $B = gn$. To make the coefficients comparable across candidates, the coefficients of each linear combination i , $c_{k,r0,i}$, denoted are normalized by dividing them by the coefficient of a reference variable X_q namely $c_{q,r0,i}$. This transformation yields normalized coefficients, $a_{k,r0,i}$, ensuring that all candidate combinations share a common scale.

¹ Artificial intelligence-based optimization techniques employ population-based search strategies. In these techniques, initial input parameters are generated randomly within defined ranges and the iterative searching processes are inspired by the behaviors of natural entities, which converge towards optimal or nearly optimal solutions. Genetic Algorithms rely on biologically inspired operators such as mutation, crossover, and selection (Holland 1975). The Particle Swarm Algorithm is inspired by fish schooling and bird flocking, so a swarm consists of the number of particles “or possible solutions” that swim or fish through space exploring optimal solutions; their position in iteration t depends on their position in $t-1$, their best position reached, and the best particle position based on overall swarm experience (Kennedy J, Eberhart RC 1995). In Ant Colony Optimization, ants are the agents that imitate the exploration of space looking for food (optimal solution), while pheromones represent chemical substances that they release along their path, which gradually diminish in strength through evaporation (Dorigo M 1992). The Bat Algorithm, inspired by the bat’s echolocation, is like the Particle Swarm Algorithm (Yang XS 2010). Elephant Herding Optimization is another example of a swarm-based search technique. In the wild, elephants from various clans coexist in herds, typically led by a matriarch. As male elephants mature, they venture out on their own but maintain communication through infrasound. This natural behavior of elephant herds has been abstracted and modelled as a clan updating operator and a separating operator in the optimization process (Wang GG, Deb S, Coelho LS 2015).

Within each group g , the n candidate linear combinations are evaluated by their Y_0 values within the window, and the combination with the highest Y_0 is retained as a survivor and proceeds to the next selection comparison. Repeating this process g times produces a reduced set of g candidate linear combinations that represent the best performers from each group.

In the third step, we do a second selection and remove the outliers from the set of g linear combinations. The criterion for identifying a linear combination as an outlier is that at least one normalized coefficient a_k of the linear combination is not in the interval:

$$[Q_1(a_k) - 3(Q_3(a_k) - Q_1(a_k)), Q_3(a_k) + 3(Q_3(a_k) - Q_1(a_k))],$$

where, $Q_1(a_k)$ and $Q_3(a_k)$ denote the first and third quartiles of coefficient of a_k , respectively. After removing outliers, a final selection stage retains the H normalized coefficient vectors that achieve the highest values of Y_0 in C_1 . These H combinations constitute the base set used to estimate the local coefficient distribution at that rank location.

The fifth step involves computing the Base Coefficient for each predictor X_k , as described in detail in Algorithm 2. Using these base coefficients, the sixth step evaluates the probability of the outcome $Y=1$, $\hat{p}_{r_0,i}$, for all observations. The observations are ordered according to their estimated probabilities. Based on this ordering, the subset of observations in C_1 is identified, which allows us to determine the observation at position $2p$. The eighth step estimates the probability in this position, denoted $\hat{p}_{r_0,i=\text{Rank}(2p)}$, which serves as the lower bound (minimum) for the predicted probabilities at the subsequent rank location r_0+1 , $\hat{p}_{r_0+1,i}^{\min} = \hat{p}_{r_0,i=\text{Rank}(2p)}$. This value serves as a continuity anchor and is required for the calculations described in Algorithm 2.

Figure 5. Algorithm 1: Procedure to find the base coefficients

In the ninth step, the window advances from C_1 to C_2 by shifting p observations along the ordered list. The first p observations are removed from the working dataset, and the same sequence of operations—steps two through eight—is repeated for the updated window. This iterative procedure continues until the algorithm reaches the final position $r_0=R$.

Algorithm 2 - Step 5: Finding the Base Coefficients for the Linear Combination i

The magnitudes of the coefficients obtained from the H linear combinations retained in Step 4 of Algorithm 1 are not directly interpretable, since they were previously normalized, as discussed in the preceding section. To recover the final scale of the coefficients for a given linear combination i , we first evaluate the corresponding score for all observations using that linear combination (Step 5.1 of Algorithm 2, Figure 6):

$$P_{r_0,i}(X) = \sum_{k=1}^K a_{k,r_0,i} X_k$$

Where $P_{r_0,i}(X)$ is the value of the linear combination and $a_{k,r_0,i}$ is the normalized coefficient associated with predictor k in linear combination i . Observations are then sorted according to the score $P_{r_0,i}(X)$ (Step 5.2). For the first m ranked observations — corresponding to window C_{r_0} — the algorithm computes the next summary statistics: (i) The mean of each predictor, \bar{X}_k , (ii) $Y_{0,r_0,i}$, defined as the number of observations with $y=0$ within the window, and (iii) $X_{k,i=Rank(1)}$, the value of each predictor X_k for the observation ranked first.

In addition, we define the probability associated with the first observation in the ranking, denoted by $\hat{p}_{r_0,i}^{\min}$. This quantity represents the lower bound of the predicted probabilities within window C_{r_0} . For the first window ($r_0=1$), no previous window exists, so the lower bound is set to zero. For all subsequent windows ($r_0>1$), the lower bound equals the estimated

probability of the observation located at rank $2p$ in the previous window, that is, $\hat{p}_{r_0,i}^{\min} = \hat{p}_{r_0-1,i=\text{Rank}(2p)}$. As discussed in the previous section, the probability at rank $2p$ acts as a continuity anchor between consecutive windows: it defines the minimum predicted probability allowed at rank location r_0 and ensures a smooth transition of predicted probabilities across overlapping segments of the ranked population.

With this information, we can calculate the mean value of $P_{r_0,i}(X)$ (Step 5.4):

$$\bar{P}_{r_0,i}(X) = \sum_{k=1}^K a_{k,r_0,i} \bar{X}_k$$

And $P_{r_0,i}^{\min}$ for the observation that ranked first (Step 5.4):

$$P_{r_0,i}^{\min} = \sum_{k=1}^K a_{k,r_0,i} X_{k,i=\text{Rank}(1)}$$

The method assumes that the mean probability in C_{r_0} is at the point S_{r_0} . At this point, the probability of $Y=1$ is $\hat{p}_{r_0,i}$ and it equals:

$$\hat{p}_{r_0,i} = \frac{Y_{1,r_0,i}}{m} = \frac{m - Y_{0,r_0,i}}{m}$$

The relationships between $\bar{P}_{r_0,i}(X)$ and $\hat{p}_{r_0,i}$ and $P_{r_0,i}^{\min}$ and $\hat{p}_{r_0,i}^{\min}$ are given by:

$$\hat{p}_{r_0,i} = \alpha_{0,r_0,i} + F_{r_0,i} \bar{P}_{r_0,i}(X)$$

$$\hat{p}_{r_0,i}^{\min} = \alpha_{0,r_0,i} + F_{r_0,i} P_{r_0,i}^{\min}$$

Where $F_{r0,i}$ is a scale factor that rescales the normalized coefficient $a_{k,r0,i}$ into the corresponding base coefficient and $\alpha_{0,r0,i}$ is the base intercept. From the two previous equations $F_{r0,i}$ equals:

$$F_{r0,i} = \frac{\hat{p}_{r0,i} - \hat{p}_{r0,i}^{\min}}{\bar{p}_{r0,i} - p_{r0,i}^{\min}}$$

The scale factor therefore restores the magnitude of the coefficients, converting the normalized linear combination into an interpretable base equation that is consistent with the local probability calibration. Once $F_{r0,i}$ has been obtained, the estimation of the Base Coefficients for linear combination i follows directly (Steps 5.6–5.7). The base intercept is computed as:

$$\alpha_{0,r0,i} = \hat{p}_{r0,i}^{\min} - F_{r0,i} p_{r0,i}^{\min}$$

while the base coefficients for each predictor are given by:

$$\alpha_{k,r0,i} = F_{r0,i} a_{k,r0,i}, \quad k = 1, \dots, K$$

Finally, the mean (and percentiles) values for the base coefficients are calculated at the end of Algorithm 2:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{k,r0} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^H \alpha_{k,r0,i}}{H}$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_{0,r0} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^H \alpha_{0,r0,i}}{H}$$

$\bar{\alpha}_{0,r0}$ and $\bar{\alpha}_{k,r0}$ are used to estimate the probability $Y=1$ of the observations, as Step 6 of

Algorithm 1 indicates: $\hat{p}_{r0} = \bar{\alpha}_{0,r0} + \sum_{k=1}^K \bar{\alpha}_{k,r0} X_k$.

Figure 6. Algorithm 2 - Step 5: Finding the Base Coefficients for the Linear Combination i

